

Heavy metals and Microbial assessment of Aguda-Ijesha canal, Lagos, Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

Canals are generally known to draw water from surrounding wetlands which then have negative impacts on surroundings. In tropical areas, residents in proximity to such canals tend to suffer from diseases such as malaria and typhoid due to the stagnancy of these canals. This study therefore, investigated the ecotoxicological and health threats of Aguda-Ijesha canal by microbiological and heavy metals analysis. Atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS) and microbiological examinations were done to water samples obtained from this canal, using standard protocols and compared with the World Health Organization (WHO) permissible limits. The microbiological analysis indicated that the canal is abundant in harmful microorganisms, with bacteria, fungi/yeast, and fecal coliform accruing counts of 4.70×10^7 , 2.0×10^3 , and 1.10×10^3 respectively. Isolated microorganisms included *Bacillus subtilis*, *Micrococcus spp*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (bacteria), *Fusarium spp* (fungi), and *Escherichia coli* (fecal coliform). Heavy metal analysis revealed that the concentrations of cadmium, copper, zinc, and lead surpassed the allowable limits recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO). The specimen contained cadmium at a mean value of 0.031 ± 0.002 , while copper had a mean value of 0.414 ± 0.002 , the mean value of zinc was 2.428 ± 0.080 , and finally, lead had a mean value of 0.033 ± 0.001 . These findings pose grave public health hazards for the inhabitants, particularly those who are close to the canal. Therefore preventive and punitive measures need to be enacted, to mitigate the amount of indiscriminate waste disposal, as well as exercises like disinfection and dredging to be done intermittently

Keywords: Heavy Metals, Pollution, Threat, Toxicity, Waste

1.0 Introduction

As urbanization and industrialization are accelerated, ecotoxicological problems are also increasing, leading to various ecological and public health concerns. Improper disposal of domestic and industrial waste containing heavy metals and other pollutants in Lagos state is increasing, particularly in the canals and other waterways [1], [2]. Canals are useful and in abundance in Lagos State and have come to be synonymous with pollution and contamination [3] Residents near these canals face the greater health risks especially during the rainy season. However, the residents in proximity to the Aguda-Ijesha canal suffer terribly from malaria and typhoid as the canal is stagnant,

eutrophicated, and has an offensive odour for most of the year [4]. This canal is known to be stagnant for most of the year, giving out a foul-smell. This is due to the immense amount of waste dumped into it, particularly organic matter, such as fecal waste causing eutrophication. The canal gets so filled up that it overflows and spills into residential buildings, private gardens, markets and shops resulting in floods while spreading its contaminated contents. Additionally, sewers and drainage systems are usually overwhelmed by floods [5]. Heavy metals are transported into the soil which are later taken in by plants [6]. These metals can cause health problems such as physical, muscular and neurological degenerative processes that mimic certain diseases such as Alzheimer's disease and

Parkinson's disease as reported by [7] as well as cancer reported by [8] for the residents who keep and cultivate small gardens near the canal. These heavy metals can also settle on the soil surface for a long time [9] and on the walls of buildings. Cadmium, for example, migrates into the atmosphere through solid waste combustion [8]. According to [10], lead (Pb); is the most important toxic heavy metal due to its physicochemical properties [11]. It is also known for accumulating in the human body via different means such as bioconcentration, and biomagnification causing harm to the nervous system as well as the renal, reproductive, cardiovascular, hematopoietic, and skeletal systems [11]. Toxic elements and microorganisms have been identified as major contaminants in the environment [12]. Therefore, according to [13] microorganisms enter the cells and disrupt the normal functioning of the immune system. Consequently, there is a need to investigate the potential harm this particular canal might be causing to the environment and possibly to the residents of this particular area. Searching the literature, there is a dearth of information on the health risks posed by canals especially those

located in residential areas. This study therefore investigated the levels, of microorganisms and heavy metals in water samples collected from the Abule-Ijesha canal, Lagos State, Nigeria.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Description of study area

This study was carried out at the Alhaji Sulaimon Street/Anjorin Street section of the canal, Lagos state, Nigeria (Figure. 1). The canal is situated between latitude 6°29' N and longitude 3°19' E Lagos spans a total area of 3,577 km², with 2,798 km² being land and 779 km² (approximately 15%) comprising water bodies [14]. The state's vegetation is tropical, and it has diverse aquatic ecosystems such as lagoons and creeks. The climate is primarily humid, with a short dry season and a long rainy season [15]. Lagos is Nigeria's most densely populated city and the second-largest metropolis in Africa. It also serves as a major financial hub for the continent and the economic powerhouse of Nigeria [15].

Figure 1: Map of Study Area (Google Images, 2023)

2.2 Sample collection

The water samples were collected in March, 2024 into three sterile glass bottles making up to 750ml, from the Alhaji Sulaimon Street/Anjorin Street section of the canal. The sterile container was thoroughly rinsed with the canal water twice

before collection and the bottle was filled up with the canal water and tightly covered. It was later transported to the chemistry laboratory of the University of Lagos, in less than twenty-four (24) hours. The samples were tightly covered and refrigerated at -10 °C in the laboratory for few hours. The water samples were frozen and then

defrosted later at room temperature (26°C) for further analysis.

2.3 Heavy metal analysis

Analysis of heavy metal concentration was done using Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS) according to methods described by [6]. The test samples were transferred to a pre-washed beaker containing analytical grade, aqua regia mixture (70% HNO₃ and HCl ratio: 3:1), and 30% H₂O₂. The mixture was digested. The solution was cooled, filtered through a Whatman No. 42 filter paper. Then the filtrate was subjected to atomic absorption spectroscopy using a spectrophotometer (UNICAM, model: 969) to determine the concentrations of selected heavy metals.

2.4 Microbial analysis

The total bacterial and coliform counts were estimated using the membrane filtration technique, as well as the two-step enrichment method for microbial growth, following the methods described by [15].

2.5 Statistical analysis

The levels of heavy metals and microorganisms in the water samples were presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD) using Excel software.

3.0 Results

The results of the levels of microorganisms in the water sample are shown in tables 1 and 2. These tables revealed the bacterial, fungal, and coliform species identified along with their respective abundance levels in comparison to each other. These microorganisms were all far above the permissible limits.

Table 1. Bacteria, fungi, and fecal coliform bacteria and their counts.

Parameter	Bacteria Count	Fungi/Yeast Count	Fecal Coliform Count
Water Sample	4.70 x 10 ⁷ ± 10000 CFU/ml	2.0 x 10 ³ ± 400 CFU/ml	1.10 x 10 ³ ± 200 CFU/ml
WHO Limit	≤ 100 CFU/mL	0 CFU/100 mL	0 CFU/100 mL

Values expressed as mean ± SD and CFU/mL; ND: not detected; WHO [23]

Table 2. List of isolated bacterial, fungal, and coliform species and their level of abundance.

Isolated Microorganisms	Abundance
<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	++
<i>Micrococcus spp</i>	+++
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	++
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	++
<i>Fusarium spp</i>	++

**Present (+), relatively abundant (++) and highly abundant (+++)-

Table 3 also shows the concentrations of heavy metals in the water samples. The levels of cadmium and lead in the water samples were

observed to have surpassed the allowable limits by the World Health Organization (WHO) except for copper and zinc.

Table 3. Heavy metal concentration in water sample and standard deviation.

Metals	Mean values (mg/L)	W.H.O Permissible Limits (mg/L)
Cadmium	0.035±0.002	≤ 0.03
Copper	0.414±0.002	≤ 0.05
Zinc	2.428±0.080	≤ 5.0
Lead	0.033±0.001	≤ 0.01

Values expressed as mean ± SD and mg/L; WHO [22], [23]

4.0 Discussion

Microbial analysis of the water samples showed they were highly contaminated with bacteria and fecal coliform. This finding is in tandem with the observations by [16] who isolated several harmful microbes like *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella* species. etc. from flood water samples in three sampling stations in Yenagoa, Niger Delta, Nigeria. [15] also observed high bacterial and coliform counts in water samples obtained from the well and borehole water samples collected from Iwaya, Makoko, and Ilaje, Lagos State. Furthermore, the result of this study is in line with that of [17] who analyzed several water samples for bacteria and coliform life from three different sampling stations in Delta State, Nigeria. [18] also found that *Fusarium* spp, found in the water sample, is an opportunistic pathogen that causes human fusariosis. In like manner [12] in their study, noticed *Fusarium* spp in water samples after hurricane Harvey and was classified as an invasive infection.

The results of heavy metals concentrations revealed that the levels of heavy metals, especially cadmium and lead, surpassed the allowable limits by the World Health Organization (WHO). This conforms to the findings of [19] who detected heavy metals in several water samples from Obio Akpor, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. In line with the findings of this study, [20] in their study on Ologe, Lagos lagoon, also found that the levels of cadmium and copper in the water samples were detected above the permissible limits. A similar report was also generated by [21] who investigated

the presence of heavy metals in a reservoir in Sahel Africa.

5.0 Conclusion

This study has revealed substantial amounts of harmful microorganisms and heavy metals concentration in the water samples obtained from Aguda-Ijesha canal, emphasizing the potential health risks associated with the residents that come into contact with this water especially during the floods. It is therefore, an unsafe body of water. Bacteria like *E. coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* exceeds safe limits and coliform counts. The selected heavy metals detected in the canal made the canal a dangerous reservoir of health risk when exposed to it. As a result, this indicates that any groundwater for consumption would require proper treatment before it is considered safe for consumption. These findings have weighty implications for environmental and public health policies.

6.0 Recommendation

Public awareness campaigns would be helpful in enlightening the local population on best practices on waste disposal and the adverse health effects upon contact with the wastewater. Proper treatment of waste water by the government should be done consistently to avoid contact with groundwater that could lead to contamination.

7.0 References

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